

Supplementary tables and figures for paper “Baraminic placement of Homo heidelbergensis based on molecular data”

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Supplementary Table 1. Frequency of the 12 SNPs in the human genome based on calculations of Guo and Jamison (2005) and the analysis of the dbSNP database.

SNP	dbSNP	Guo and Jamison
A>C	4.7%	4.4%
A>G	16.4%	16.6%
A>T	4.1%	3.7%
C>A	4.5%	4.4%
C>G	4.2%	4.7%
C>T	16%	16.6%
G>A	16%	16.6%
G>C	4.2%	4.7%
G>T	4.5%	4.4%
T>A	4.1%	3.7%
T>C	16.4%	16.6%
T>G	4.7%	4.4%

Supplementary figure 2a. Treemap showing the frequency of the twelve different SNP types for five ERR samples with reads from *H. heidelbergensis* mapping to hg38.

Supplementary figure 2b. Treemap showing the frequency of the twelve different SNP types for five ERR samples with reads from *H. heidelbergensis* mapping to the Neanderthal genome.